

Be Better Informed
About Fertility

To give voice to citizens towards improving
Assisted Reproduction Technologies (ART) for society!

Why is it important?

In a few years, around **10% of the population born in Europe will be the result of assisted reproduction techniques (ART)**, and about half of the population that wishes to have children will go to specialized centers.

Therefore, Assisted Reproduction Technology (ART) plays a **significant role in the reproductive health of European society** and is a fast-growing part of the health industry.

Objectives

- 1** Promote the participation of society in the field of ART
- 2** Test an Innovative co-creation methodology
- 3** Create a roadmap for ART
- 4** Provide information to policymakers responsible for the legal conditions of ART
- 5** Collect, analyse and transfer social scientific knowledge

How Will B2-Inf do this?

DATA COLLECTION

By collecting, analysing and transferring social scientific knowledge, expectations and concerns about ART to clinics and policy makers, focusing especially on the younger generations.

OFFERING INFORMATION

By improving the scientific information offered by the ART clinics to society from the sociocultural, legal and gender perspective through recommendation guidelines.

THE RESULT?

Readily available and practical National and International guidelines for ART clinics, specifically designed to close the gap between expectations of society and available solutions.

Finally, solutions **MADE FOR YOU.**

subscribe to our newsletter

b2-inf.eu

[/company/b2-inf-h2020-project/](https://www.linkedin.com/company/b2-inf-h2020-project/)

[@b2inf_](https://twitter.com/b2inf_)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 872706

